

AEoT: AN INITIAL FRAMEWORK OF AESTHETIC EXPERIENCE OVER TIME.

Ioana Ocnareescu¹ Jean-Baptiste Labrune¹ Frédérique Pain¹ Dominique Sciamma²
Carole Bouchard³ Améziane Aoussat³

¹Alcatel-Lucent Bell Labs France, ²Strate Collège Designers, ³LCPI Arts et Métiers ParisTech France
ioana_cristina.ocnareescu, jean-baptiste.labrune}@alcatel-lucent.com

ABSTRACT

Different contributions in the design research community propose models to understand subjective experience with products. Recently, the temporal aspects of experience have particularly been highlighted, leading to initial studies of experience over time. In addition, many researchers interested in experience, addressed its aesthetic qualities. However, the temporal structure of the aesthetic experience has been rarely addressed in the design research community. In this paper we clarify these concepts and we introduce an initial framework of aesthetic experience over time. Our framework focuses on three structural components: body and senses interaction, discourse elements and narrative dimension and has three goals. Firstly, we will show how to apply it as a descriptive framework, by allowing representing a significant range of existing aesthetic experiences in order to understand, accommodate and appropriate them. Secondly, we discuss its potential to be evaluative, permitting to analyze and compare the experiential potential of design situations in regards of aesthetic experience over time. Finally, we investigate its generative power, how it helps the creation of future aesthetic experiences.

Keywords: Aesthetic Experience, Temporal structure, Narrative, Discourse, Body.

1. INTRODUCTION

Aesthetic Experience – between design principles and creating place for subjectivity and appropriation

There is definitely a challenge within the design community to understand what are the 'ingredients' or qualities to take into consideration in order to understand what makes a good product experience

and furthermore how to create it. "Although one might try hard as a designer, an experience cannot be guaranteed" (Hassenzahl & Carroll, 2010) writes Hassenzahl in his latest book on Experience Design. Some objects resonate with some people and not at all with others. *Subjectivity* seems to be the general characteristic when trying to define product experience (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007), (Hekkert & Schifferstein, 2008) and when it comes to define aesthetic experiences - these 'special' experiences that go beyond appearance towards more personal and relational ways of living with objects, some researchers sustain that there is no final definition on such complex concept (Ross & Wensveen, 2010). Therefore a clarification on the definitions of the concepts of experience and of aesthetic experience is still a challenge in today's design research community. And moreover, once this matter is understood, how to create these experiences? Different frameworks, principles and rules were developed in the last ten years that try to clarify the most important aspects to take into consideration when analyzing or trying to create aesthetic experiences with products.

From the principles and rules perspective, we believe that creating aesthetic experience is more than following strict guidelines and that "the best designers sometimes disregard the principles of design. When they do so, however, there is usually some compensating merit attained at the cost of the violation" (Lidwell, Holden, & Butler, 2010). The idea is also underlined by Hassenzahl: "experience emerge from a variety of aspects, many of them beyond the control of design... some outstanding experiences may come without careful crafting..." (Hassenzahl & Carroll, 2010). So the challenge for design research is related to the tension between being rigorous using scientific knowledge to predict the impact of the design intention and the openness for subjectivity to the mysterious "human motivation... tied to subconscious instincts, perceptions and influences" (Kimberly Elam in (Lidwell, Holden, & Butler, 2010)). More than other concepts in design research, designing for aesthetic experience is related to this tension.

From the frameworks perspective, we observed a variety of purposes related to these frameworks and

thus their operationalization is not clear. Are they useful for analyzing and understanding subjective accounts of users' experiences or, to inform and predict the creation of appropriate future experiences? Therefore, in this paper, we analyze different research frameworks from the design research community, clarify their different epistemological aspects and intentions, and extract common aspects to propose our own theoretical framework. This framework will not only describe and analyze the potentiality of products and situations to engage people in aesthetic experiences, but also focus on their creation, and investigate how practitioners and researchers might operationalize such research to manifest experiential aesthetic qualities in their future works.

2. FRAMEWORKS ON EXPERIENCE AND AESTHETIC EXPERIENCE

A. GENERAL MODELS, THEORIES AND FRAMEWORKS ON EXPERIENCE

Defining the concept of experience in design is not a simple research task. 'All About UX' website (<http://www.allaboutux.org/>) extracted 27 different definitions on user experience from the research in this field. Moreover in February 2011 the research committee of this community wrote a white paper on the 'user experience' concept that tries to clarify this concept or at least underline the challenges for the design research to use this concept (Seminar & Experience, 2011). Different frameworks that come from HCI – Human Computer Interaction and interaction design community like (Forlizzi & Battarbee, 2004; Forlizzi & Ford, 2000) or industrial design like (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007; Hekkert & Schifferstein, 2008) try to visualize the experience as a system between a user, a product and the interaction in a socio-cultural context. However the complexity of this concept visualized in this manner makes its operationalization almost impossible. Therefore the lack of a unified framework or even a consensual definition of user experience is something underlined by different researchers in the domain (Blythe, Hassenzahl, & Law, 2009).

However we believe that initial foundations exist in different frameworks that we are going to analyze and discuss further on. The purpose of this chapter is to underline different elements of two different frameworks (Forlizzi & Ford, 2000) and (Karapanos, Zimmerman, Forlizzi, & Martens, 2009) for a theoretical integration, continuation and application of the research in this domain towards the exploration of the concept of aesthetic experiences in design research.

However, before discussing these frameworks, having a general definition of experience, permits us to position ourselves among the different perspectives in which experience is studied in design science. We are interested in a definition that shows what means living

an experience, as “interaction between (a) live creature and enviroing conditions” (Dewey, 2005). Therefore we propose the following definition of an **Experience**:

An extra-ordinary situation that modifies human beings in a conscious and unique way.

The word extra-ordinary in this definition means that this situation is not ordinary and that the self-consciousness of the person is needed to perceive the remarkableness of the experience. However even with this definition there are different levels of perceiving and living such an experience. Trying to find the limits of this definition, we will also encounter the notions of “everyday experience” and of “life experience”. The difference between these two limits is the impact of an experience on human life, the degree of transformation that comes during the experience. And how could design practitioners use this definition to create potentiality into products for this type of Experience. As Forlizzi et al. underline “as designers trying to craft an experience, we can only design situations, or levers that people can interact with, rather than neatly predicted outcomes” (Forlizzi & Ford, 2000). So what are the theoretical frameworks that could help a designer to describe, evaluate or generate design situations with a experiential potential?

In a first study of UX created by Forlizzi et al. in 2000, they propose a tool to classify and describe experience with products. Forlizzi makes a distinction in this paper between *experience* - “a series of activities that have been collapsed into a routine”, also known as a subconscious experience, and *an Experience* - “an experience (that) has a beginning and an end, and changes the user, and sometimes, the context of the experience as a result” (Forlizzi & Ford, 2000), following Dewey's constructionist approach. The third term proposed, *experience as a story*, could correspond to a temporal evolution of the first two, *experience* and *An experience*. An important contribution of this paper is how they break apart this concept into four dimensions: sub-consciousness, cognition, narrative, and storytelling. We are particularly interested in the storytelling dimension of this framework. It brings into exploration both the temporality of the experience and the interpretation that we could obtain from the users' perspective on their experiences with particular design situations. Therefore a *narrative dimension* condenses the appropriation of the experience, both its anticipation and consummation and could embrace all subjective aspects of an Experience.

However, experience is more than “an episode, a chunk of time that one went through” (Hassenzahl & Carroll, 2010). Another important step in the recent research in this field, is the interest in the dynamic nature of the experience, when the time factor becomes an important step for the understanding of experiences (Evangelos Karapanos et al., 2009). In

their study of experience over time, Karapanos et al. identify three temporal phases in the adoption of mobile phones: orientation, incorporation and identification. Using Grounded Theory on 482 users' stories, they studied what a satisfying experience means in each phase depending on different variables: familiarity, functional dependency and emotional attachment. Their results show that the factors that influence user experience over time evolve with the relation between the user and the product. Even if there is a belief that anticipation and expectation are important to the overall experience, the actual experience is more influenced by how the product becomes meaningful in users' lives.

B. GENERAL FRAMEWORKS ON AESTHETIC EXPERIENCE

The concept of aesthetic experience is a controversial notion to define and apply to design research. Some researchers try to define this concept from a philosophical ((Folkmann, 2010; Petersen, Iversen, & Krogh, 2004)□□, phenomenological (Folkmann, 2010) or cognitive perspective (Lidwell et al., 2010). Other researchers position themselves by understanding how the interaction between a person and an object could become an aesthetic experience (Locher, Overbeeke, & Wensveen, 2009)□ and others try to emphasize what are the aesthetic qualities of an object (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007). Udsen and Jørgensen□ propose in their paper 'The Aesthetic turn' four approaches that explore the concept of aesthetics in HCI research field: *the cultural approach, the functional approach, the experience-based approach and techno-futurist approach* (Udsen & Jørgensen, 2005)□. Among all these studies we position ourselves in the experience-based approach, from a pragmatic perspective.

Using both Dewey's and Shusterman's theoretical frameworks for understanding the aesthetic aspects of an experience, we describe the aesthetic experience as a mixture of "bodily sensation and an intellectual challenge ... connected to context, use and instrumentality ... prolonged beyond the immediate experience" (Shusterman, 2000)□. Thus the *body* and *the senses* are primordial for Shusterman's definition on experience. Concerning the temporality of the aesthetic experience over time, we underline the fact that the aesthetic judgment is a complex process that takes time and preparation (Shelley, 2009)□. The *intellectual experience* is highlighted in both theories of Shusterman's and Dewey's as an important part of aesthetic experience, since it creates a space for meaningful stories and personal interpretation. e Concerning the creation of the aesthetic appreciation, Shelley describes this operation as a complex process (Shelley, 2009)□. What gives value to an art-work are the art-historical *context* and the *category* in which the object is classified before judgment. They also introduce the notion of *preparation* before aesthetically judging an object. The preparation consists in knowing the intentions and the social

context of the creator, taking into considerations the external factors that contributed to the creation of the art-work and determining a category in which this work should be judged. In order to sum up all this type of rational information that a person could gather within his/her relation with an object, we propose *discourse* as a form for operationalization.

Following the different aspects on the concept, we identify a tension between two philosophical movements that are also present in design research. The question that differences the two major perspectives on Aesthetic, is the following: "What can a theory of aesthetic experience be that takes seriously the distinction between the experience of features and the features of experience?" (Shelley, 2009)□. It is a philosophical fight between the value of the experience, "an object has aesthetic value insofar it affords valuable experience when correctly perceived" (Shelley, 2009)□ versus the experience of value, when the aesthetic character lies within the object. We position ourselves in the first perspective, *from the experiential point of view* but in our definition we also take into consideration the *experiential aesthetic potential carried by the object*. Thus we define an **Aesthetic Experience** as following:

An embodied Experience that was lived due to the qualities of the experienced object and the persons capacity to be transported beyond them.

In design science, one of the perspective of studying aesthetics of interaction is the pragmatic aesthetics approach coined by (Petersen, Iversen, & Krogh, 2004)□ from Shusterman theory on pragmatic aesthetics (Shusterman, 2000)□□. Their framework consists in three aspects: *social-cultural aspects, instrumentality of the experience and mind and body interaction*.

Like other researchers that talk about the aesthetics of use (Dunne, 2008)□ rather than the aesthetic of the appearance, and define the aesthetic experience as a "construction of relations between artifact and viewer, subject and object, user and tool" (Wright & McCarthy, 2008)□, Petersen et al. emphasize the fact that designing for aesthetic experiences invites people to actively participate in creating sense and meaning. This approach is similar to *reflective beauty, an intellectually driven process* (Norman in (Blythe & Hassenzahl, 2004)□), that differs from others approaches: behavioral – perceptually driven and visceral – expectation driven. In this paper we are interested in following the experience-based approach proposed by (Petersen et al., 2004; Wright & McCarthy, 2008)□ and we introduce a first theoretical framework of aesthetic experience over time. Three aspects will be discussed in the following section: *the narrative dimension, the discourse elements and the body and senses interaction*.

3. CREATING A FRAMEWORK

A. DESIGNING A FRAMEWORK

There are different intentions at stake when creating a framework. Beaudouin-Lafon highlights how interaction models for interactive applications “must strike a balance between generality (for descriptive power), concreteness (for evaluative power) and openness (for generative power)” (Beaudouin-Lafon, 2004)□. **Descriptive** frameworks allow to represent a significant range of existing experiences in order to understand, accommodate and appropriate them. **Evaluative** frameworks permit to analyze, compare and assess different design objects and situations using experiential criteria. Finally, **generative** ones help the creation of future experiences. In the design field, we find some examples of descriptive frameworks like (Petersen et al., 2004)□ or evaluative frameworks like (Karapanos et al., 2009)□. However we find their use unclear as generative ones. Our goal in this paper is to create a framework that besides its descriptive potential – to explain and demonstrate, could also serve as a foundation for the creation of evaluative and generative methods for aesthetic experiences.

From a constructivist point of view, designing a theoretical framework also shows us the **didactical** potential of this research in terms of understanding aesthetic judgments. Therefore we want to investigate how this framework could assist non-experts in developing their capacities for living aesthetic experiences and understanding their aesthetic sophistication. This research as a guideline could help them to focus on different points to take into consideration when interacting with a design object.

B. TEMPORAL DESCRIPTION OF AN EXPERIENCE

Recent studies on user experience show the importance of understanding this notion more than out-of-the-box experience towards the study of the evolution of experience over time (Karapanos et al., 2009). A white paper on UX describes the temporal aspect of experiences from the point of view of design practice: anticipated UX, momentary UX, episodic and cumulative (Seminar & Experience, 2011)□. Hassenzahl talks about micro, meso, macro experimentation time (Hassenzahl & Carroll, 2010)□ and Karapanos et al. analyze two temporal levels of the experience: the anticipated experience and the actual experience with a product, and how the relation between a person and a product evolves in these experiential states – anticipation, orientation and incorporation.

We integrate all these aspects and we present a timeline of an Experience in Figure 1. We chose to break the experiential potential in two time spans, that of *direct use*: First Encounter, Momentary Experience and Direct Experience with a design object, and that of *non-direct use*: Pre-Experience, In between Experience and Post-Experience. The *design object* is

a materialized design intention, a product, a service etc. and further on we will describe the six temporal spaces where the experience with this design object could occur:

Pre-Experience is created from all the information gathered before the first usage with the design object. The experience with other design objects and the brand experience is also included in this stage. The amount of information creates the *anticipated experience* and the *expectation* on how the design object will be meaningful into the person's life.

First Encounter is the first interaction with the design object, usually a brief moment that regroups the visceral responses of both the appearance and the interaction and brings new information about the design object. The orientation phase, that refers to users' initial excitement and frustration with the design object, also starts during this first momentary experience (Karapanos, Hassenzahl, & Martens, 2008).

Momentary experience regroups all the experiences between the First Encounter and the long term experience with the object, called Direct Experience. For example, before buying an object, one could see it in a store, try it during different occasions, and only after these short temporal interactions, decide to buy the object and start the direct experience. More information will be incorporated during this level and, like in the First Encounter, the orientation and the expectation could change.

During **Direct Experience**, the person passes through different experiential phases like: orientation, expectation, incorporation and identification as showed in (Karapanos, Hassenzahl, & Martens, 2008). During these phases different aspects of the experience like familiarity, functional dependency and emotional attachment lead to the satisfaction that a person has within the relation with the object.

Post Experience, the last level proposed by this temporal model is the one that starts with the closure of direct interaction. If we extract ourselves from the technological context where most of the studies in this field are held, and take for example the experience of an exhibition in a museum, the Post-Experience starts when the person leaves the museum. Even if the Direct Experience is over, the Post-Experience could be a part of the overall experience, if the person continues thinking about the exhibition, understands new things by talking with people etc. Therefore we believe that the study of this span of time and how to design the post-experience is important for the continuation or the closure of the overall experience. As Hassenzahl underlines in (Blythe & Hassenzahl, 2004)□, people interpret, reflect, appropriate and recount, and the dialogical process of storytelling others and ourselves about what was experienced could open new possibilities for the understanding of the experience and for its prolongation.

Figure 1 also presents the three components of Aesthetic Experience, the body and senses, the discourse and the narratives, that are developed in the next subsection. Our intention with this visualization was to show how this temporal model could be used in order to study user experience over time. An application of this temporal model that gathers also the elements presented in the framework of the aesthetic experience will be discussed in the fourth section. Once these time spans are defined, we could consider them a new base for discussion of the different results from the literature on the subject.

Different hypothesis could be made concerning the importance of each temporal level for the overall experience. For example Karapanos et al. argues that the actual experience, the Direct Experience as we defined it previously, is more influential than expectations, i.e. the Pre-Experience (Karapanos et al., 2009)□. Other researchers show how repeatability and the long use of an application could bring engagement only after interacting with the object for a considerable amount of time (Bradley & Lang, 1994)□.

Figure 1 Temporal structure of an Experience

In this case, where pre-experience is not created and where expectation and anticipation are not the attributes that create the 'magic power' of the experience, repeated usage permits users to understand, identify and engage themselves gradually in the experience.

By proposing this temporal model, we try to establish the foundation for understanding how the Experience – the extra-ordinary situation, is created and how each temporal level contributes to its creation. Moreover we are interested in how the aesthetic aspects of this experience act in each temporal phase, how they are mixed to create an overall aesthetic experience and how the experience could be prolonged and simulated within the non-direct use phases. The next subsection presents three experiential aspects that we define as being the aesthetic experience components. □

C. AESTHETIC EXPERIENCE COMPONENTS

In the previous chapter we presented the different aspects that design research took into consideration when describing aesthetic experiences. The knowledge and the high interest on this specific topic come from an urge to explore the different dimensions of technology and its place in our everyday life. Therefore defining aesthetic experiences and experiences in the design community is closely related to a technological context. With our framework we try to generalize this research to larger class of design objects and to understand how a dynamic relation and an aesthetic experience could be developed over time with interactive objects but also to less technological ones.

Why looking at The Red Blue Chair of Gerrit Rietveld or at a well-known painting (see Figure 2) could interpellate us in such a profound way, even if we never lived with these objects in our daily lives, while an 'ordinary' armchair, that we 'touch' everyday, could pass unnoticed? What is the 'special' power of the experience with this kind of objects besides the fact that they are socio-cultural symbols? Is it related to the fact that we do not own them, and that we value this lack of presence, like in the mechanics of desire? How a design object could live and grow in us and how our experience with this object transforms ourselves over time?

Figure 2 The Red Blue Chair (left) and people looking at Gioconda – Louvre Museum (right)

In this chapter we emphasize that living such experience depends on the meaning we create for a certain design situation – the personal *story* that people imagine during the interaction with the object, how the information about this object was created over time – the *discourse* and how we interact with the object – the *body and senses interaction*.

a) The narrative dimension

In a recent paper on Experience Design, Hassenzahl discusses the qualities of a good experience with products. He talks about the Philips *Wake-Up Light* that has “the power to ‘transcend its encasing’”, due to the fact that it creates meaning, a story that emerges “from the dialogue of a person with her or his world through action”. Therefore the experience is an imagination exercise seen as a dialogue between the person and the object. The space for the aesthetic experience is filled up due to the objects properties perceived by the person- *the rational discourse*, but once this discourse is perceived and understood, the imaginative human capacity gives a meaning to the interaction with that particular object.

The same author presents two qualities of the User Experience: *pragmatic* and *hedonic* (Hassenzahl & Carroll, 2010). In order to underline the interconnection and distinction between these two qualities he gives an example with a person that wears high heels. The pragmatic quality is related to the shoes function, their instrumentality: “shoes are made for walking” (Hassenzahl & Carroll, 2010)□, the hedonic quality is related to how these shoes transform the person that wears them, socially, culturally and personally: “shoes make me feel admired... physically changed”(Hassenzahl & Carroll, 2010)□.

Going a little bit further we could add that these objects give the person a role to play, they set the scene for a *transformation* and *transportation*. Both of these terms could be associated to Dewey’s perspective on *An Experience* that has a potential to change user’s behavior during such interaction.

Thus experiential objects – objects to be experienced, do have *transformable and transportable power*. We call this quality the **Narrative quality** and we define it as following:

The narrative quality transports the user towards a space that elicit the imagination and that is connected to the user’s imaginary. It is within this intersection between user’s imagination and imaginary where meaning and stories are born and where subjectivity and appropriation have a potential to be developed.

Musso describes the concept of imaginary as “the network of images, discourses, myths and narratives intertwined with the production and use of services , technologies and products” (Musso, Ponthou, & Seulliet, 2007). This space contains all the cultural and social symbols and frames the social-cultural context for an aesthetic potential. It makes possible the dialogue that a person creates to experience the world. It is within this intersection between user’s imagination and imaginary, where meaning and stories are born and where subjectivity and appropriation have a potential to be developed. We identified five steps within this narrative dimension that gradually create the personal story of the person (see Figure 3):

- ✦ transportation – the object acts like a metaphor (from Greek - meta: with, across, after and pherō: “I bear, carry” and also literally from μεταφορά - transport),
- ✦ *imagination* – the person starts to imagine a story, a fiction,
- ✦ connection to *imaginary* – to all dynamic combinations of social and cultural symbols, universes and norms,
- ✦ meaning and *story creation* – the dimension that a person subjectively invests the experimented situation,
- ✦ *integration* – the story is appropriated and integrated in the person’s memory.

Figure 3 The three dimensions of the Aesthetic Experience framework

b) The discourse elements

The discourse elements are the objective facts and properties of the experience within an object, a service or a socio-material situation.

Like the narrative dimension, these elements of an aesthetic experience are dynamic and created over time through different steps (see Figure 3):

- *contextualization*, the discourse is created even before the interaction with the object from passed experience in a learning process. In addition, discourse elements are always situated, part of a context either physical, semiotic or socio-cultural. The situatedness of discourse elements make them manifest or salient (like contrast of color tones for instance) but can also modify their dimensions or perceptive qualities (like optical illusions or gestalt organizational paradoxes). Suchman propose the action and thus the interaction should be a dialogue between people and 'rhetorical devices' related to a specific context (Suchman, 2007). And sometimes, only the context can disambiguate the meaning and intentions of discourse elements afforded by an object.
- *description, classification and organization* of the object properties during the interaction with the object. Hekkert et al. define the aesthetic object as an object designed as appealing, that gives pleasure and delight (Hekkert & Schifferstein, 2008)□. Choosing from the 125 design principles presented in (Lidwell et al., 2010)□, they classify the design properties that determine the aesthetic appreciation into three different categories. The psychological properties are the formal qualities of the object like intensity, size, color, hue, saturation, brightness. The organizational properties are edges, contours, blobs, basic geometrical shapes "we like to look at patterns that allow us to see relationships or create order" (Hekkert & Schifferstein, 2008). Being conscious about these properties could also lead in the understanding of the object as 'dialogue' language between the person and the object.
- Finally, the *integration* phase brings the user to gather, mix and integrate other information from other sources, like discussion with people, reading a menu or a guiding book etc.

The discourse elements are important for the comprehension of how an object will integrate our life and will extend the space for dialogue and appropriation.

With their concept of *slow technology*, Hallnäs and Redström present an example, 'Informative art'

application, that 'amplifies' the art object's capacity to present information (Hallnäs & Redström, 2001)□. Therefore the presentation, which we call here the discourse around the object, could create potential for a better understanding and resonance with the object.

Both the narrative dimension and the discourse create a dialogue between a person and an object. Another concept that could gather this type of relation is *imaginative rationality* coined by Lakoff and Mark Johnson. They talk about metaphors and they argue that these forms of imagination not only make our thoughts more vivid and interesting but that they actually structure our perceptions and understanding. "The reason we have focused so much on metaphor is that it unites reason and imagination. Reason, at the very least, involves categorization, entailment, and inference. Imagination, in one of its many aspects, involves seeing one kind of thing in terms of another kind of thing—what we have called metaphorical thought. Metaphor is thus imaginative rationality" (Lakoff & Johnson, 1981). However the way to reach this imaginative rationality depends on the interaction with the world. The next subsection will present the last component of our framework, the body and senses interaction and its importance in the creation of an aesthetic potential.

c. Body and senses interaction

The last component of our framework is closely related to the notion of embodiment of the person within the interaction. The concept of somaesthetics developed by Shusterman places the body as a central indicator of our experience within the world. He defines *somaesthetics* as "the critical study and meliorative cultivation of how we experience and use the living body (soma) as a site of sensory-aesthetic appreciation (aesthesia) and creative self fashioning". This perspective offers a connection between "everyday bodily practices and corresponding ways of being in the world that might contribute to what he refers to as 'a more global art of living'" (Kimberly Powel, 2010)□. Peterson et al. use this concept and the pragmatic aesthetics of Shusterman in their framework for describing aesthetic experiences as bodily experiences with intellectual dimensions.

Following the same approach, we define the **body and senses interaction** dimension as :

The capacity of human beings to interact and create knowledge with the world through their bodies and senses.

This dimension has the following components (see Figure 3):

- *interaction with the object's representation* – before interacting with an object, the person might perceive a representation of the object;
- *static affordances* – the person perceives and understands different properties of the object

using all senses but touch and body interaction and *dynamic affordances* – the person perceives and understands through action and interaction with the object;

- *interaction* - how the person interacts with the object in his everyday life;
- and *embodiment* – the progressive bodily integration of the interaction with the object.

4. FRAMEWORK APPLICATION

□ In section 3 we presented the temporal structure of an Experience and the three components that could bring the experiential potential. The purpose of this section is to propose uses of these elements and their evolution over time for when describing, evaluating and creating potentiality for aesthetic experiences. With this chapter we construct an initial theoretical framework of aesthetic experience over time.

A. DESCRIBING EXPERIENCES WITH EXISTING DESIGN SITUATIONS

One of the role of our framework is **to describe** the experience one can sustain with representations and socio-material situations over time. Like many other elicitation protocols such as the ones we have seen in section 3, the framework invites us to express how the experience manifests. In these three examples, we will examine how the aesthetic experience potential evolves over time, especially in terms of its relation to embodiment, discourse and narration. In addition, we chose artefacts from three different contexts: a picture in a design-oriented context, a lamp prototype coming from design research and a commercial product from an experimental design collection. These three design objects were chosen as we considered that different researchers talked about their aesthetic potential and therefore we wanted to describe their potential using our framework. For the moment the description provided in this paper rests a subjective description. Future work on this framework would permit us to have less subjective descriptions about these three objects and consequently a better understanding of the descriptive 'force' to grasp the aesthetic potentiality.

The first object to describe was a photo of Philippe Ramette's *Object with which to see the world in detail / use of the object* (Figure 4a), that is presented by Dunne in the chapter Aesthetics of use (Dunne, 2008). The picture is the design object of the artist. However the photo presents a design object and its use and, Philippe Ramette invites the user to project him/herself to experience its use through an intellectual exercise. In order to understand what could be the aesthetic potential of this representation, we filled up the following table (Table 1) with one of the authors subjective experience with this picture. We underline the temporal evolution of the relation between the viewer and the representation through narration episodes followed by a textual synthesis of

the recounted experience that we present in Table 1.

□ **Figure 4** Philippe Ramette : *Objet à voir le monde en détail / utilisation de cet objet* (1990).

a. A digital representation of the picture created by Philippe Ramette (*Sourcing : librairie-carterie du Centre Pompidou*, 2009); **b.** *The First Encounter with the representation* – picture from ((Dunne, 2008)□, page 56); **c.** *The Direct everyday Experience with this presentation - a post card in a desk office.*

	Body & Senses	Discourse	Narratives
Pre-Experience	-	-	-
First Encounter <small>initial brief encounter between a person and the experienced object</small>	gaze-following, remarkable emotion difficult to name almost like an emotional shock	book semantic context, both semantic and representational	Story of the book told from Tony Dunne personal point-of-view + the story of the strangeness of the picture situation
Momentary Experience <small>other brief encounters</small>	gaze-following the mountain shape from the image, emotion of introspection	Assemblage of discourse related to the visual composition identification of the context from the picture and its different elements.	Imaginative stimulation through the identification of a tension and ambiguity of the plot
Direct Experience <small>episodic encounters that involve long term use and relation creation.</small>	Somatic memory of nature, meditative and calm feeling	Detailed navigation through the picture elements, analyzing in details the object and the person.	Imaginative stimulation and questioning: Where is this taking place, what led this man here with all his gear and why doesn't he look at the table ?
Post Experience	Peripheral attention cue, calming and subtle action of the senses	Going through the different elements rapidly, explaining them to other people	Telling the stories of Ramette, of this picture and of my stories invented around this representation.

Table 1 The application of the Aesthetic Experience framework over time for Philippe Ramette's *Object with which to see the world in detail / use of the object* (1990)

The second object chosen for our study is Philip Ross's lamp AEI presented in (Ross & Wensveen, 2010) that became a product called Fonckel□ in 2012 (Figure 5a, the product and Figure 5b, the design research object). The author describes the AEI lamp to have an aesthetic potential through its process – designing for aesthetic interaction through aesthetic interaction, and due its qualities to create an dialogue that involves people's bodily, cognitively, emotionally and socially (Ross & Wensveen, 2010).

We present our experience with this object through the different temporal phases of the experience. Doing so we realized the difficulty that design community sometimes encounter to actually have a Direct Experience with research objects. Usually the experience and the comprehension of the use with a research object is created by reading papers and understanding others' experiences. However some of

the authors of this paper had the opportunity to actually interact with this object and the descriptive approach of our framework permits them to share their experiences (see Table 2).

Figure 5 Philip Ross's lamp AEI (2011) / Fonckel (2012)

- a. A digital representation of the product - Fonckel lamp created from AEI lamp (Sourcing : <http://www.fonckel.com/>);
- b. The Pre-Experience with a representation of the AEI lamp when reading the article (Ross & Wensveen, 2010a);
- c. The First Encounter with AEI lamp and interaction with the object.

	Body & Senses	Discourse	Narratives
Pre-Experience	-	Description of shape of object with hands, drawing of the lamp by a colleague; reading the Ross paper; description of attributes and abilities of this lamp	A story about how the lamp is animated like a character, stories about related animated products such as Apple advertisements as inspiration for AUR, DockLamp and LuminAR lamps
First Encounter <small>initial brief encounter between a person and the experienced object</small>	Reacting to the different levels of luminosity when approaching to the lamp; Touching the shell of the lamp, trying different kind of caress, slow touch, poking	Confrontation to the affordances of the lamp; Description of the lamp functions by Philip Ross, inspection of details	Free association of the shape of the lamp with an animal like a snake; An animated story between the AEI lamp and a classic architect lamp
Momentary Experience <small>other brief encounters</small>	-	-	-
Direct Experience <small>episodic encounters that involve long term use and relation creation.</small>	-	-	-
Post Experience	-	Reading Philip Ross PhD and better understanding the theoretical context; Seeing the future of this design research object as a product by discovering the website of Fonckel lamp-	Stories related to this lamp in the context of design research

Table 2 The application of the Aesthetic Experience framework over time for Philip Ross's lamp AIE (2011)

The last design object chosen for our analysis is the Tree-trunk bench designed by Jurgen Bey within his collaboration with Droog Design group. The choice of this product is both related to the easiness to interact and create a personal experience with this type of design objects in the Droog Design shops, but also from a general point of view on Droog Design way of exploring the aesthetic potential for everyday products. Dunne describes this design collective in the Introduction of Hertzian Tales as “cultural and aesthetic experiment design group” (Dunne, 2008) □ as they propose with their objects alternatives to perceive and to be engaged differently with our surroundings. The Tree-trunk bench object, as other products from Droog Design occupy not only a space in our environment, but also a space in our imagination and buying a bench becomes buying a story, a cultural manifest : “it is ridiculous to transport trees when they are locally available”. We could also add that the high price of 11 000 € of this design

object could also place an important role the experience creation. Table 3 present our experience with this product and Figure 6 comes to complete the understanding though different representations.

Figure 6 Jurgen Bey for Droog Design: Tree-trunk bench and another public tree-trunk bench.

- a. A digital representation of the product (Sourcing : <http://www.droog.com/store/furniture/tree-trunk-bench/>);
- b. First Experience and interaction with the design object;
- c. Public tree-trunk bench – Paris

	Body & Senses	Discourse	Narratives
Pre-Experience	-	Size of the object, explanation of the conceptual space of this design when told by a friend	Stories about Droog Design, Jurgen Bey and other Droog curated designers
First Encounter <small>initial brief encounter between a person and the experienced object</small>	Seating on the bench, walking on it, being seated close to other people (this was at Salone del Mobile, a design fair with many people)	Comparing the actual object features with what I expected it to be like in real-life; Inspecting closely the object, the details of the reclining details, the texture of the wood	Associations from the materiality of the object, tree, forests stories, emphasized by the fact that the bench was presented in the context of an enchanted forest Hearing the stories people told about this object and its hypothetical purposes, Stories about Droog
Momentary Experience <small>other brief encounters</small>	-	-	-
Direct Experience <small>episodic encounters that involve long term use and relation creation.</small>	-	-	-
Post Experience	Experiencing another bench that look like Tree-trunk bench	Seeing pictures of this object often in catalogues and on the web; Discussions about this object with colleagues and friends as an example of an object that assemble different styles and design purposes; comparison with other benches;	Many stories about my experience of seeing this object for real, stories to try to understand how its price is justified by imaginative power.

Table 3 The application of the Aesthetic Experience framework over time for Jurgen Bey Tree-Trunk Bench for Droog

The three tables that were presented above try to detail the subjective experience and the authors of this paper had during the experience with the non technological design objects. This exercise showed the complexity of describing experiences beyond the actual direct experience and how the construction of meaning become a dynamic process that mixes the narrative dimension, the discourse elements and the embodiment of the information that comes from the interaction with the body and the senses. The description of these components showed the empty spaces and potentiality for aesthetic experience and how the relation with the three objects is recalled at a certain moment in time. For examples seeing the Gioconda in Louvre Museum could be considered as a rare Direct Experience, but seeing different representations in films or art-books change our relation with the painting. Finally we believe that the aesthetic potential might come from other sources that direct use through the evolution of the meaning and its

embodiment during other temporal spaces like First Encounter or In-between Experience. Until now, these spaces were ruled by marketing and publicity for business purposes. However the designers could also explore these areas by creating open spaces for stories and personal appropriation. This perspective could bring value for the persons' overall experience with their surroundings.

B. EVALUATING DESIGN SITUATIONS

The aesthetic experience as we describe it in this paper has its central interest in studying the *perceived experience evolving over time*. Rather than studying the aesthetic qualities of design objects we are interested in understanding the aesthetic of an experience, what makes a memorable or aesthetic moment. We join our efforts with other researchers that consider such experiences as “the way an object speaks to us, calls us, affords us, puts us into contact with others, is meaningful to us, shares its inner horizon with us. ... we hope to reconcile the experiential with the rational, to reconcile feeling with thinking” (Hummels & Overbeeke, 2010).

Following this experiential approach, evaluating aesthetic experiences is a complicated task. The first difficulty is the *dynamic aspect of the experience that changes continuously over time*. Today few studies like (Karapanos et al., 2009)□ and (Karapanos, Zimmerman, Forlizzi, & Martens, 2010) showed the different temporal phases in the adoption of products and how their personal satisfaction with these products changes over time.

Another difficulty comes from the complexity of the experience creation and evolution and its gradual evaluation over time. From our point of view there are two different types of evaluation, **real-time evaluation** – that implies that the evaluation system 'records' the way the persons feel and think during their interaction with the design object. The challenge of this evaluation, that uses techniques and tools that come from neurosciences - like the eye-tracker or electrodermal measurement devices, is to be the more subtle and the less invasive as possible. Another type of evaluation is **recount evaluation** where experiences are gathered as a collective of subjective experience narration, bits of episodes.

An example of a method from this category used by design researchers is the Day Reconstruction Method (DRM) (Kahneman, Krueger, Schwarz, & Stone, 2004)□ used in studies like (Karapanos et al., 2009)□. The Experience Sampling Method (ESM) is another method developed by Csikszentmihalyi that tries to grasp the person's perceived experience in a intrusive thus subtle way by asking participants to stop from their activities and write down note on their experience in real time. However the complexity of an aesthetic experience might be difficult to extract and analyze using the method per se. A combination of these methods could be suitable for understanding how the

narrative dimension and the discourse elements evolve over time. But how to understand the tight relation between the body and the senses, the complexity of embodied actions?

In order to evaluate experiences, usually design researchers use methods and tools that come from psychology like all the methods enumerated above. However designers could bring their experience and understanding on user-experiences and participate to the creation of future tools and set-ups to grasp subjectivity and understand the evolution of user-experience over time.

In our attempt to collect subjective insights and stories related to Aesthetic Experiences, we created Aesthetic Experience Catchers*. Our goal was to make people talk about different situations and moments when they lived an aesthetic experience, to try to explain these complex situations with people's stories and their post-feeling. We talked with 15 different persons and we asked them three questions: *Could you give us a short definition, personal and informal of an aesthetic experience? Could you tell us a story where you felt you were going through an extra-ordinary moment that you would consider as an aesthetic one? If you were to characterize or describe what you feel during these moments in 3 words, what would they be?* The stories per-se do not provide useful information about aesthetic experiences. However what we found relevant for our research was *the structure of people's experiences, their evolution through time, and the fact that the post-experience are re-enacted through narration*. People recall such moments and share their experiences by trying to be *rational* but also through an *imaginative context*, which combined, might make us enter into a subjective space and live together such experience. Following Hassenzahl description of an experience as “a packaged labeled, integrated with our knowledge of the world and stored away” (Hassenzahl & Carroll, 2010)□, Aesthetic Experience Catchers* wanted to open and relive such 'aesthetic packages' and to share through narration and rational discourse to a post-experience.

C. GENERATIVE FRAMEWORK

Using generative frameworks does not necessary mean that these framework will help designers to create new objects or new interactions. We believe that in the field of user experience research, we should also focus on how to make the experiential potential understandable, how to extend the experience beyond its use toward a personal appropriation through story and meaning creation.

Therefore we introduce the concept of **elasticity of experience** that acts in other temporal spaces than the Direct Experience of use. Thinking about an object, creating stories and having a personal relation with a specific object is a subjective and dynamic process.

One of the future goals of our research is to evaluate how the framework could generate an aesthetic potential for objects already designed. What *Jurgen Bey's* bench teaches us? After all, it is just another bench. But the discourse and the narratives that this object spread makes us re-look at the object and understand that is not a 'just a bench'. The object tells a story and this makes it 'special' and even 'so special' that it becomes embodied in ourselves— when sitting on another bench one of the authors re-experienced a moment spent on the Tree-trunk bench. Therefore we believe that one of the generative power of this framework is the exploitation of the non-direct use temporal spaces for a better understanding and appropriation of the relation between a person and a design object. Like Beaudouin-Lafon, we believe that “generative power does not mean allowing the computer to automatically generate canned solutions, but rather helping human designers create richer and more varied design spaces from which to develop innovative solutions” (Beaudouin-Lafon, 2004). And maybe these solutions are related to how we could perceive differently the design objects□. For us the experience designer should create spaces for reflection incorporated in the design object. It is more than creating directions for use; it is about creating directions for experience.

Finally, our future work will focus on how to fill these reflective spaces during post-experimentation and how to create Aesthetic Experience Triggers* during the non-direct use experience. Hassenzahl et al. present in their book *Experience Design: Technology for All the Right Reasons*, an unpublished study of an evaluative experience on user engagement over time. They show how prolonged and repeated use made the persons engagement with a gaming application evolve gradually over time (Hassenzahl & Carroll, 2010)□. Therefore the actual design object and the interaction with such complex objects might not be enough to completely create a potential for experiences. Maybe working on creating spaces for moments of reflection like the projects presented by (Hallnäs & Redström, 2001) on Slow technology could bring useful information for the research in experience creation and its evolution over time.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

“HCI quite naturally focuses on the interactive products, the 'thing' rather than the experiences resulting from interacting with the thing” (Hassenzahl & Carroll, 2010)□. For us the “thing” as Hassenzahl calls the design object is like a *light bulb*. It has physical properties like *luminosity* (*the emitted amount of light*) that can be measured but also has other properties, less rational and less measurable like *brightness*. Brightness is a subjective attribute of the luminosity perceived from the light bulb. Therefore evaluating aesthetic experience means for us evaluating the brightness of an object, its radiating light.

In order to study this subjective information, we proposed in this paper to break the temporal structure of an experience in two different moments: the moments of *direct use* where the person interacts with the design object and the moment on *non-direct use* where the person gathers other type of information that contributes to the overall experience. Each of these temporal spaces are segmented in temporal phases like First Encounter, Momentary Experience and Direct experience for the direct use, and Pre-Experience, In-between Experience and Post-Experience for non-direct use.

Once this structure presented, we propose three components of aesthetic experience - the narrative dimension, the discourse elements and the body and senses interaction. We showed how this theoretical framework could be used as a descriptive framework and both the evaluative and generative potentials were discussed.

Finally, we think that the narratives and the discourse, the imaginative rationality is a way of creating a subjective and long lasting relation and connectedness between a person and a design object. Hence we believe that the best experiential products will be those that “more than anything else manifest their owner’s access to the best knowledge, information and accumulated wisdom to be had” (Blythe, Hassenzahl, & Law, 2009b) and that could transform the experience into a relationship.

6. REFERENCES

- Beaudouin-Lafon, M. (2004). *Designing Interaction, not Interfaces. AVI'04* (pp. 15-22). ACM.
- Blythe, M., & Hassenzahl, M. (2004). Interview with Don Norman. *Interactions Magazine*.
- Blythe, M., Hassenzahl, M., & Law, E. (2009). Now with Added Experience? *New Review of Hypermedia and Multimedia*, 15(2), 119-128. doi:10.1080/13614560903251100
- Bradley, M., & Lang, P. J. (1994). Measuring emotion: the Self - Assessment Semantic Differential Manikin and the Semantic Differential. *Science*, 25(1).
- Desmet, P., & Hekkert, P. (2007). Framework of Product Experience. *International Journal*, 1(1).
- Dewey, J. (2005). *Art as Experience* (p. 371). Perigee Trade. Retrieved from <http://www.amazon.com/dp/0399531971>
- Dunne, A. (2008). *Hertzian Tales: Electronic Products, Aesthetic Experience, and Critical Design*. The MIT Press. Retrieved from <http://www.amazon.com/dp/0262541998>
- Karapanos E., Zimmerman, J., Forlizzi, J., & Martens, J.-B. (2009). User Experience Over Time: An Initial Framework. *CHI 2009 Proceedings*, 0, 729-738.
- Folkmann, M. N. (2010). Evaluating Aesthetics in Design□: A Phenomenological Approach. *Design Issues*, 26(1).
- Forlizzi, J., & Battarbee, K. (2004). Understanding experience in interactive systems. *Proceedings of the 2004 conference on Designing interactive systems processes, practices, methods, and techniques - DIS '04*, 261. New York, New York, USA: ACM Press. doi:10.1145/1013115.1013152

- Forlizzi, J., & Ford, S. (2000). The Building Blocks of Experience: An Early Framework for Interaction Designers. *Human-Computer Interaction*.
- Hallnäs, L., & Redström, J. (2001). Slow Technology – Designing for Reflection. *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing*, 5(3), 201-212. doi:10.1007/PL00000019
- Hassenzahl, M., & Carroll, J. (2010). *Experience Design: Technology for All the Right Reasons [Broché]* (p. 100). Morgan & Claypool Publishers. Retrieved from <http://www.amazon.fr/Experience-Design-Technology-Right-Reasons/dp/1608450473>
- Hekkert, P., & Schifferstein, H. N. J. (2008). Introducing Product Experience. *Product Experience* (pp. 1 - 8). Elsevier Science.
- Hummels, C., & Overbeeke, K. (2010). Special Issue Editorial: Aesthetics of Interaction Where Do We Stand Now? What is Our View on the Aesthetics of, 4(2), 1-2.
- Kahneman, D., Krueger, A. B., Schwarz, N., & Stone, A. (2004). The Day Reconstruction Method (DRM): Instrument Documentation, (July), 1-56.
- Karapanos, E., Hassenzahl, M., & Martens, J.-B. (2008). User experience over time. *Proceeding of the twenty-sixth annual CHI conference extended abstracts on Human factors in computing systems - CHI '08*, 3561. New York, New York, USA: ACM Press. doi:10.1145/1358628.1358891
- Kimberly Powel. (2010). Somaesthetic Training, Aesthetics, Ethics, and the Politics of Difference in Richard Shusterman's Body Consciousness. *Action, Criticism & Theory for Music Education*. Retrieved from http://act.maydaygroup.org/articles/Powell9_1.pdf
- Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1981). *Metaphors We Live by [Broché]*. University of Chicago Press. Retrieved from <http://www.amazon.fr/Metaphors-We-Live-George-Lakoff/dp/0226468011>
- Lidwell, W., Holden, K., & Butler, J. (2010). *Universal Principles of Design, Revised and Updated: 125 Ways to Enhance Usability, Influence Perception, Increase Appeal, Make Better Design Decisions, and Teach through Design* (p. 272). Rockport Publishers. Retrieved from <http://www.amazon.com/Universal-Principles-Design-Revised-Updated/dp/1592535879>
- Locher, P., Overbeeke, K., & Wensveen, S. (2009). A Framework for Aesthetic Experience. *Advances*, 9-12.
- Petersen, M. G., Iversen, O. S., & Krogh, P. G. (2004). Aesthetic Interaction — A Pragmatist's Aesthetics of Interactive Systems. *DIS2004*.
- Ross, P. R., & Wensveen, S. A. G. (2010). Designing Behavior in Interaction: Using Aesthetic Experience as a Mechanism for Design. *International Journal*, 4(2), 3-13.
- Marc Hassenzahl. (n.d.). User experience and experience design. Retrieved January 17, 2012, from http://www.interaction-design.org/encyclopedia/user_experience_and_experience_design.html
- Musso, P., Ponthou, L., & Seulliet, É. (n.d.). *Fabriquer le futur 2: L'imaginaire au service de l'innovation*. Village Mondial. Retrieved from <http://www.amazon.fr/Fabriquer-futur-Limaginaire-service-linnovation/dp/2744062642>
- Seminar, D., & Experience, D. U. (2011). USER EXPERIENCE WHITE PAPER. *Seminar*.
- Shelley, J. (2009, January). The Concept of the Aesthetic. *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. The Metaphysics Research Lab. doi:10.1111/1467-9973.00225
- Shusterman, R. (2000). *Pragmatist Aesthetics: Living Beauty, Rethinking Art* (p. 368). Rowman & Littlefield. Retrieved from <http://www.amazon.fr/Pragmatist-Aesthetics-Living-Beauty-Rethinking/dp/0847697657>
- Suchman, L. (2006). *Human-Machine Reconfigurations: Plans and Situated Actions* (Cambridge., Vol. 99, p. 328).
- Udsen, L. E., & Jørgensen, A. H. (2005). The aesthetic turn: unravelling recent aesthetic approaches to human-computer interaction. *Digital Creativity*, 16(4), 205-216.
- Wright, P., & McCarthy, J. (2008). Aesthetics and Experience-Centered Design. *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction*, 15(4), 1-21. doi:10.1145/1460355.1460360